

MODE I INTRALAMINAR FRACTURE TOUGHNESS OF GLASS FIBER-REINFORCED POLYMERS FABRICATED WITH DUCTILE MATRICES

Davi M. Montenegro¹, Francesco Bernasconi, Markus Zogg¹, Paolo Ermanni², Matthias Gössi³, Rafael Libanori⁴ and André R. Studart⁴

¹Innovative Composite Structures, Inspire AG
Technoparkstrasse 1, CH-8005 Zurich, Switzerland
Email: davi.montenegro@inspire.ethz.ch, zogg@inspire.ethz.ch

²Composite Materials and Adaptive Structures Lab, Department of Mechanical and Process Engineering, ETH Zurich
Leonhardstrasse 21, CH-8092 Zurich, Switzerland
Email: permanni@ethz.ch

³Corporate Research, Sika Technology AG
Tüffenwies 16, CH-8048 Zurich, Switzerland
Email: matthias.goessi@ch.sika.com

⁴Complex Materials, Department of Materials, ETH Zurich
Vladimir-Prelog-Weg 5, CH-8093 Zurich, Switzerland
Email: libanori@mat.ethz.ch, andre.studart@mat.ethz.ch

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ABSTRACT

The range of applications of fiber-reinforced polymer (FRP) materials with thermoset matrices is in some cases restricted due to their low damage tolerance. While particle-toughening can be effective in increasing the damage tolerance of these materials, problems with manufacturing or significant decrease in T_g and stiffness of the toughened resin are often mentioned as major drawbacks. Here we used a novel thermoset polyurethane (PU) resin as an alternative to a commercial epoxy (EP) matrix system for the production of unidirectional glass fiber-reinforced polymer (GFRP) laminates. We investigated the quasi-static behavior of these laminates by means of flexural tests in both longitudinal and transverse directions and their intralaminar fracture behavior by determining R-curves of the 90° layers for the opening mode. Remarkably, the critical energy release rate J_{IC} of the PU-based laminates increased by 700% as compared to that of the EP-based laminates with only about 35% decrease in the flexural stiffness and strength of the 90° layers,

1 INTRODUCTION

Fiber-reinforced polymers (FRPs) with thermosetting matrices are nowadays the material of choice for applications where high specific strength and stiffness and good processability are important design parameters. Examples of applications include the aerospace, automotive and marine industries as well as the construction branch (e.g. bridges) and sports industry (bicycle frames, ice hockey sticks, tennis rackets etc). Although broad, this range of applications is in certain cases restricted due to the rather damage-intolerant character of these FRPs.

The common approach to circumvent this problem is to extrinsically toughen a given strong and brittle matrix. [1] – [16] This is commonly achieved by adding rubber- (or soft) or ceramic-like (or hard) particles to the matrix. Examples of soft particles include hyperbranched polymers and liquid rubbers (see references [1] and [2] for reviews). These materials are the most effective ones in providing toughness to the brittle polymer they are added to. The main toughening mechanism

reported in such cases is localized shear yielding between the rubber particles [1] [2]. Toughening with hard particles is in general less effective than with soft particles (chapter 3 in [13]) and has been mainly made with alumina [3], silica [4] [5] and chalk [6] particles, or with carbon nanotubes [7]. Crack pinning [8], crack deflection [9], shear band yielding in the polymer [10] and particle debonding with subsequent plastic void growth [11] have been reported as toughening mechanisms acting in this case. Up to 10-fold improvements in the fracture toughness of modified epoxies were reported by using a mix of soft and hard particles in [12].

Whereas the aforementioned toughening strategies do yield tougher matrices, they also present some drawbacks. A simultaneous drop in the composite's T_g [13] and stiffness [14] are noticed in the case of soft-particle toughening. On the other hand, hard-particle toughening maintains or even increases stiffness and T_g [15] [16], but it usually worsens the processability of the toughened FRPs by increasing the viscosity of the polymer. Furthermore, filtering of particles by the fibers can lead to inhomogeneous particle distribution within the composites when liquid composite molding processes are used. Finally, the material costs of some inorganic particles pose an additional challenge to manufacturers of FRP parts. The range of applications of FRPs could be therefore expanded by having composites with improved fracture toughness at a mild penalty in stiffness and strength that maintained their good processability.

In this work we used a novel and more ductile thermoset polyurethane matrix as an alternative to the commonly used epoxy-based resins. Due to the compatible chemistry of the PU with silica, PU-matrix GFRP laminates are expected to have strong fiber/matrix interfaces, which should lead to composites with improved intralaminar fracture toughness [17]. The mechanical performance of the pure matrices and of unidirectional plies out of EP- and PU-matrix GFRPs was evaluated by means of 3-point-bending tests. In addition, the matrices and 90°-layers of GFRPs had their mode I fracture toughness evaluated by means of J-integral measurements.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2-mm thick pure matrix plates were produced by resin transfer molding (RTM) with two steel molds of dimensions 600 x 300 x 25 mm³. A scheme is shown in Figure 1a and the materials used are listed in **Error! Reference source not found.**

Figure 1: (a) Scheme of the layout used in the resin transfer molding process for the fabrication of the matrices; (b) Scheme of the layout used in the vacuum assisted resin transfer molding process for the fabrication of the unidirectional GFRP laminates. For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the digital version of this article.

Material	Manufacturer	Catalog number / commercial name	Country
Epoxy Resin	Sika Schweiz AG	SikaDur 300	Switzerland
Unidirectional glass fiber non-crimp fabric	Tissa Glasweberei AG	850.80.0445.0600	Switzerland
Vacuum bag	Airtech Europe Sarl	Wrightlon® 7400	Luxembourg
Polyethylene hoses	Festo Belgium nv	PEN-Ø8x1.25-NT	Belgium

PTFE hoses (for PU-based laminates)	Thai Scan Tube Co., Ltd.	FSPTFE0600080	Thailand
Distribution medium	Airtech Europe Sarl	Greenflow 185	Luxembourg
Peel-ply	Airtech Europe Sarl	Stitch Ply A	Luxembourg
Breather	Airtech Europe Sarl	Airweave® N4	Luxembourg
Sealant tape	Airtech Europe Sarl	AT-200Y	Luxembourg
Mold release agent	Axel Plastics Research Laboratories, Inc.	XTEND 832	USA

Table 1: Materials used in the RTM and VARTM processes.

The commercial epoxy resin, named here EP, was mixed by hand for 5 min and degassed for 10 min before being injected under partial vacuum. Cure took place at 80 °C for 2 hours and post-cure at 125 °C for 3 hours. The polyurethane resin PU, provided by Sika Technology AG, was mixed in a mixer system (DAC 150 FVZ, FlackTek Inc., USA) at 2500 rpm for 1 min and was injected immediately after that. Cure took place at room temperature for 8 hours and post-cure at 80 °C for 3 hours. All plates cooled down naturally to room temperature before demolding. 3-point-bending specimens with nominal dimensions 60 x 25 x 2 mm³ were cut with a precision cut-off saw (DIADISC 4200, Mutronic GmbH & Co. KG, Germany) and tested (Z250 SW, Zwick GmbH & Co. KG, Germany) with a span L of 32 mm at a cross-head speed of 1 mm/min, following the recommendations of ISO 178. [18] Stresses and strains were calculated according to Equations 1 and 2, which take into account the curvature of the loading pin to provide accurate values for deflections greater than 0.1L. [19]

$$\sigma = \frac{3FL}{2bh^2} \left\{ 1 + 6 \left(\frac{d}{L} \right)^2 - 3 \left(\frac{dh}{L^2} \right) \right\} \quad (1)$$

$$\varepsilon = \frac{h}{L} \left(6 \frac{d}{L} - 24.37 \left(\frac{d}{L} \right)^3 + 62.17 \left(\frac{d}{L} \right)^5 \right) \quad (2)$$

Where σ [MPa] is the tensile stress at the outer surface of the central cross-section of the beam, ε [-] is the strain experienced at the point where σ was calculated, F [N] is the resulting force, b [mm] is the specimen's width, h [mm] the specimen's thickness and d [mm] is the applied displacement.

Unidirectional GFRP laminates of nominal thickness 2 mm (layup: [0]₆) were fabricated for 3-point-bending tests by vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (VARTM). Figure 1b shows a scheme of the layup strategy. The fibers were impregnated with either one of the two resins EP and PU. The fibers were dried under vacuum ($P \leq 0.07$ bar) at 100 °C for 2 hours for the fabrication of the PU-matrix laminates to avoid foaming of the resin during cure due to the interaction of the isocyanate with the air humidity. Rectangular panels of 200 x 300 mm² were impregnated at room temperature. The laminates were cured in the same conditions as the pure matrices. The plates cooled down naturally before demolding. Specimens with nominal dimensions 60 x 15 x 2 mm³ were machined for 3-point-bending tests and were tested in both longitudinal (0°) and transverse (90°) directions with a span L of 40 mm at a cross-head speed of 1 mm/min, following the recommendations of ISO 14125. [19] Stresses and strains were calculated according to Equations 1 and 2.

The fracture toughness of the pure matrices and of the 90° layers of the laminates was evaluated by measuring crack-resistance curves (R-curves) through the compliance method [20] for the opening mode (Mode I). 5 mm-thick plates out of the pure resin and of unidirectional GFRPs were prepared by RTM. The single edge-notched beam (SENB) specimen configuration was used with nominal dimensions L 30.0 x W 5.0 x h 2.5 mm³ and span width S of 20 mm. The notch, with a length of about

2 mm, was machined with a diamond wire saw equipped with a 0.3 mm diameter filament. The initial pre-crack was then prepared by continuously sliding a razor blade (thickness: 0.2 mm, tip radius: ca. 10 μm) cyclically inside the notch at 1 Hz until the total crack length a (notch + pre-crack) accounted for $0.45 \leq a/W \leq 0.55$. This last procedure was performed with the custom-made machine shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Custom-made machine used to generate the initial cracks in the SENB specimens

The testing procedure and data reduction technique are thoroughly described elsewhere [21].

We have fitted the function $J = C1(\Delta a + \delta)^{c3}$ to the obtained data, where δ is a correction to the crack extension that incorporates the effects of the testing conditions. We report the results as a function of the corrected crack extension $\Delta a_{corr} = \Delta a + \delta$. The J_{IC} values were obtained according to the procedure described in ASTM E1820 [20] using Δa_{corr} . The critical effective stress intensity factor $K_{IR,C}$ was calculated by taking the square root of the product between J_{IC} and the flexural modulus.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Quasi-static mechanical performance

System PU is 36 % less stiff and 23 % less strong than EP but presents considerably higher ductility (Table 2): specimens fabricated with PU do not break up to 20% strain, whereas those fabricated with EP fail much sooner, at around 7.9 % strain. In addition, the PU system showed 30% higher yield strain than EP. This is believed to stem from the heterophasic nature of PU, which provides an additional degree of freedom on the tuning of its mechanical properties as compared with the amorphous EP. Both systems presented a considerable amount of plasticity, characterized by the difference between the yield strain and strain at break. This deformation was indeed non-recoverable as seen in the post-test analyses of the specimens.

System	Flexural modulus (GPa)	Bending strength (MPa)	$\epsilon_{yield} = \frac{\sigma_{max}}{E}$ (%)	$\epsilon_{\sigma_{max}}$ (%)	ϵ_{break} (%)
EP	3.26 ± 0.02	119.3 ± 0.3	3.66 ± 0.02	4.56 ± 0.06	7.92 ± 0.14
PU	2.07 ± 0.44	91.5 ± 9.9	4.36 ± 0.32	5.90 ± 0.38	No break up to 20%

Table 2: Results of the 3-point-bending tests with pure matrix specimens Given are mean values (number of specimens ≥ 5) and standard deviation.

The mechanical performance of the 0° layers of the PU laminates showed virtually the same stiffness as the EP laminates and slightly lower strength (Table 3). Although the PU matrix is less stiff than EP, the laminates presented the same stiffness because upon loading in fiber direction this property is mainly dictated by the fibers. The laminates presented a predominantly brittle behavior and

post-failure analyses showed that the specimens failed on the side subjected to tensile stresses. Concerning the 90° GFRP layers, the PU laminates presented 15% higher yield strain and 43% higher strain at break at the expense of 23% and 33% in strength and stiffness, respectively (Table 4). A penalty in stiffness and strength is noticed because the response of the laminate is more affected by the properties of the matrix upon transverse tensile loading. It can also be seen that the PU laminates presented a considerable amount of plasticity. The EP laminates failed in a predominantly brittle and catastrophic manner. The PU counterparts showed on the other hand a rather ductile failure: at first the specimen lost stiffness continuously and became eventually negative; then a swift 20 % decrease in force relative to the maximum one was accompanied by the visual onset of damage; this was followed by a continuous, slow-paced decrease in the force during damage propagation.

Matrix System	Flexural modulus (GPa)	Bending strength (MPa)	$\epsilon_{yield} = \sigma_{max}/E$ (%)	$\epsilon_{\sigma_{max}}$ (%)	ϵ_{break} (%)	Specimen thickness (mm)
EP	33.6 ± 0.9	1020 ± 90	3.04 ± 0.24	3.18 ± 0.30	3.19 ± 0.31	1.93 ± 0.04
PU	33.2 ± 0.5	950 ± 40	2.86 ± 0.12	2.96 ± 0.16	2.96 ± 0.16	2.12 ± 0.05

Table 3: Results of the 3-point-bending tests with unidirectional GFRP laminates loaded in fiber direction (0°). Given are mean values (5 ≤ number of specimens ≤ 7) and standard deviation.

Matrix System	Flexural modulus (GPa)	Bending strength (MPa)	$\epsilon_{yield} = \sigma_{max}/E$ (%)	$\epsilon_{\sigma_{max}}$ (%)	ϵ_{break} (%)	Specimen thickness (mm)
EP	9.00 ± 0.39	84.5 ± 9.6	0.94 ± 0.09	1.05 ± 0.13	1.05 ± 0.13	1.94 ± 0.04
PU	6.00 ± 0.27	64.6 ± 3.1	1.08 ± 0.03	1.41 ± 0.06	1.50 ± 0.06	2.08 ± 0.05

Table 4: Results of the 3-point-bending tests with unidirectional GFRP laminates loaded in transverse direction (90°). Given are mean values (5 ≤ number of specimens ≤ 7) and standard deviation.

3.2 Fracture toughness measurements

The pure matrix systems were tougher than their respective GFRPs (figure 2a). PU exhibited stable crack propagation over a wider range of crack extensions when compared to EP. For the range of crack extensions obtained, both systems presented rising R-curves. Peak toughness values reached by EP and PU were 2.3 and 7.15 kJ/m² for crack extension of ~ 0.3 and 0.35 mm, respectively. Because the most common form of damage initiation in multidirectional GFRPs under tensile loading is cracking in the 90° layers [22] [23] [24][24 – 26], R-curves were obtained for the 90° layers of EP- and PU-GFRPs. The PU-GFRPs presented considerably tougher fracture behavior than the EP-GFRPs (Figure 2a), reaching peak toughness 1.74 kJ/m², which is 6-fold higher than the peak value of ~ 0.3 kJ/m² obtained for the EP-GFRPs.

Figure 3: Crack-resistance curves of the materials in terms of (a) J-integral and (b) the effective stress intensity factor K_{IR} . The data were fitted to the function $J = C1 \cdot (\Delta a + \delta)^{C2}$ with the least squares method. (c) Critical energy-release rate J_{IC} and critical effective stress intensity factor $K_{IR,C}$. (d) Percentage of the nonlinear part of J as a function of crack extension, where the points were connected with straight lines as a viewing guide. For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the digital version of this article.

Regarding the stress intensity factor-based description of the R-curves, it can be seen that the transfer of toughness from the matrix to the laminate was much more effective in the PU system (Figure 3b). The K -values and the fitted curves obtained for the PU and the PU-GFRP lie much closer to one another than those of the respective epoxy counterparts. Unlike in the J -values, both EP and PU systems presented very similar crack-growth behavior in K -values, which is due to the difference in their flexural moduli. For higher crack extensions, the PU system showed a tougher behavior, with peak values of K_{IR} reaching 3.75 MPa.m^{1/2}, roughly 36 % higher than the peak value of EP. The PU-GFRPs presented much higher crack-driving forces than the EP-GFRPs despite the difference in the elastic moduli of the matrices, with peak values reaching 3.25 against 1.3 MPa.m^{1/2}, respectively.

The PU and PU-GFRPs not only outperformed the EP and EP-GFRPs regarding the peak toughness values, but also the critical energy-release rate J_{IC} and the critical stress intensity factor $K_{IR,C}$ (Figure 3c). J_{IC} was 94 % higher for the PU system and that for the PU-GFRP was surprisingly 8-fold higher than that for the EP-GFRP. The difference in $K_{IR,C}$ for the matrices is not as high as the J_{IC} because of the different flexural moduli of the materials, but was still slightly higher for PU. In the laminates the difference is once again striking: the $K_{IR,C}$ of the PU-GFRP is 120 % higher. It is remarkable that the sharp increase in fracture toughness of PU-GFRPs was achieved with a strength reduction of only about 30 % when comparing the pure matrices with one another.

Finally, our observations suggest that the fracture mechanisms involved during crack propagation in all the materials studied are strongly nonlinear, especially in the EP-GFRPs (figure 3d). The contribution of inelastic phenomena to the crack-driving force increases for both resins and laminates with increasing crack extension. In the EP-GFRPs, J_{in} contributes significantly to the total crack-

driving force already at low crack extensions. The results obtained for PU and PU-GFRPs are more alike to one another than the respective results for EP and EP-GFRPs, meaning that the inelastic contribution for the fracture toughness in the PU laminates is similar to that of the matrix. As opposed to that, systems EP and EP-GFRPs have very distinct inelastic contribution. The reasons for that require further investigations and were out of the scope of this work.

4 CONCLUSIONS

We analyzed the quasi-static performance and the fracture toughness of a commercial epoxy system (EP), a prototype polyurethane system (PU) and unidirectional GFRPs made with either of the two systems as matrix (EP-GFRP and PU-GFRP). The flexural behavior of the 0° (or load-carrying) layers of the PU-based GFRP laminates was similar to that of the EP-based ones. The 90° GFRP layers, in which the onset and propagation of damage play an important role in determining the lifespan of FRP laminates [25] [23], with PU matrix presented 750% higher J_{IC} than the epoxy counterpart at a penalty of 35% in flexural stiffness and strength. By analyzing the results, we conclude that the investigated PU system has the potential of producing GFRP laminates with strongly improved damage tolerance at a very mild penalty in the static flexural properties.

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